

INTERNET AND ITS IMPORTANCE IN YOUTH EDUCATION

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Abstract. *In the era of rapidly developing times, the education of young people is an urgent topic today. Especially young people's obsession with Internet and computer games worries not only parents, but everyone. At the state level, attention is now being paid to the education of the young generation. Let's talk about some aspects that cause our youth to become addicted to the Internet and computer games and how to prevent them.*

Keywords: *internet, information society, global information network, youth education, social networks, consumer culture.*

ИНТЕРНЕТ И ЕГО ЗНАЧЕНИЕ В ОБРАЗОВАНИИ МОЛОДЕЖИ

Аннотация. *В эпоху бурно развивающихся времен воспитание молодежи сегодня является актуальной темой. Особенно увлечение молодежи Интернетом и компьютерными играми беспокоит не только родителей, но и всех. На государственном уровне сейчас уделяется внимание воспитанию подрастающего поколения. Давайте поговорим о некоторых аспектах, которые вызывают у нашей молодежи зависимость от Интернета и компьютерных игр, и о том, как их предотвратить.*

Ключевые слова: *интернет, информационное общество, глобальная информационная сеть, образование молодежи, социальные сети, культура потребления.*

INTRODUCTION

In any modern country, information has always served as the main tool for the direct delivery of events and incidents in the life of society to the consumer, and for the formation of people's consciousness, worldview, socio-political and legal culture.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In fact, the development of techniques and technologies during the last twenty years has led to an incomparable expansion of media, information sources and information suppliers (libraries, archives, the Internet, etc.) and has made it possible for citizens to use and exchange its huge volume. As a result, citizens have the opportunity to evaluate the reliability of this information, to fully exercise their rights to freely express their opinion.

Due to the abundance of information available worldwide, media and other information services (libraries, archives, and the Internet) help people make decisions. In addition, they are the means by which they can learn the truth about the community, support communication with the population, and thereby move toward the goal in unison with it.

The 21st century is the century of information technology development, and it is difficult to imagine today's development without the global information network - the Internet. It is known that the Internet is an international system that connects computer networks that provide mutual exchange of information and documents.

RESULTS

Today, the Internet opens the door to a wide range of opportunities for young people. They can walk around the world's libraries through the global network without leaving home,

become a distance (virtual) student of a higher education institution located on the other side of the world, even provide electronic services (translation of texts, preparation of video and audio products, pagination of books and pamphlets and etc.) you can even earn money. So, there are many positive aspects of the Internet.

Also, young people have the opportunity to hold online conferences, improve online skills, and have quick, cheap video or audio communication with relatives and acquaintances through social networks. In these aspects, the Internet has recently overtaken television, radio and other media in terms of attractiveness.

However, it is worth noting that, along with many useful aspects of the Internet, there are also negative consequences. The slowness of the information consumption culture among the population, especially among young people, the lack of knowledge, skills and skills in distinguishing what is necessary from the flow of various messages is the reason why some people fall under the influence of malicious people and currents, and fall into the disease of Internet addiction. According to experts, Internet addiction is recognized as a disease in the People's Republic of China, and special hospitals have been established to treat it.

By the way, in the data, experts emphasized that today the number of Internet service users is increasing year by year, and most of them are young people, there are serious social problems in this regard, that is, it is necessary to pay serious attention to the issue of their spiritual education.

After all, in addition to the acceleration of globalization processes, social networks have become the most important and indispensable means of communication between mankind today, and 63% of all mankind use the Internet.

The number of Internet users has increased by 200 million in a period of almost 1 year. The majority of Internet users (92.4%) use the Internet through mobile devices. 4.65 billion users actively use social networks. These figures show once again how important the online world is.

At the moment, in the process of globalization, which is rapidly changing, the Internet, which managed to show its comprehensive impact on all spheres of our life, is also interpreted as a form of mass media. Unlike traditional mass media, the Internet is a decentralized system, which means that anyone can communicate with others on the Internet, get information, and publish their information. Such activities are done quickly and cheaply on the Internet.

In fact, the Internet has become one of the most effective and influential mass media today. Most importantly, today the Internet is a factor in the development of human culture.

Because, according to experts, without denying the advantages of the global network, the dangers of its influence on the spirituality of young people, at the same time, there are sites of organized criminal groups and terrorist organizations in several countries of the world, through which not only information exchange, but also the lifestyle of young people, customs they emphasized that foreign ideas and practices that are completely incompatible with our customs are being propagated, that the fact that every hundredth page of the Internet has pornographic content can harm the education and morals of the young generation.

Today, young people make up about 25 percent of the world's population. That is, about 2 billion people under the age of 30, most of which are in developing countries and Central Asia. We can see that this rate will increase in the last decade and this process is mainly happening in our region. In our country, more than 60 percent of the population is made up of young people.

Therefore, today concepts such as Internet culture, virtual culture, information culture, culture of correct use of information are taking place in our lives. This means that the urgent problems of young people, such as correctly determining their place in the Internet world and correctly dealing with users, forming the skills to correctly analyze information in the virtual world, are becoming the demand of the time.

DISCUSSION

In general, the worst aspect of Internet addiction is that it leads to serious consequences, such as forgetting the real world and the duties and responsibilities of humanity. A person begins to forget the need to live in real life, to work honestly, to learn, to fulfill his duties seriously, to serve his country selflessly, and to benefit those around him.

A person who spends a lot of time on the Internet has a state of abstraction and isolation. This creates the ground for him to be destroyed and zombified by "third forces" in the future. It is no coincidence that today, destructive groups mainly use the Internet to influence the minds of young people. Another negative aspect of the Internet is the fact that selfishness, conceit, and egocentrism, in modern terms, increase the evil of people. In order to prevent this, it is necessary to revive spiritual and ideological propaganda in educational and public institutions, to deeply inculcate the nature and extent of ideological threats to young people.

CONCLUSIONS

1. Without denying the advantages of the Internet service, it should be emphasized that there are many shortcomings and neglects in the use of these opportunities.

2. It can be concluded from the results of the research that one of the urgent problems today is the need to form a culture of using the Internet among young people. In order to fulfill this task, it is necessary to increase the effectiveness of the process of teaching young people about information technologies, to properly organize the provision of information about the main subjects in the information space and their goals.

3. It is necessary to achieve the reality and implementation of activities aimed at the meaningful organization of free time of pupils and students based on the internal capabilities of the regions.

4. Based on the taste, knowledge and potential of local specialists and organizers in educational institutions, it is necessary to organize various activities aimed at introducing the Motherland and the nation in classes, clubs, meetings, dialogues and scientific conferences.

5. Realizing that the role of literature and art in the education of national pride and national culture is extremely important in the minds of young people, creating sites on literature, science, music, art, sports, and other social and humanitarian fields in communication, thereby serving the tradition and national development it should be emphasized that the development of new, unconventional and effective methods and methods of preserving values without problems is of particular importance.

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